

THE ROLE OF METHODOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF DIDACTIC CULTURE OF FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article presents the role of methods of formation of the didactic culture of future history teachers, the main directions of the teacher's skills, social relations, and his main tasks.

Key words: methodological culture, information culture, teacher, information systems, lesson, method, future.

РОЛЬ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ДИДАКТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ИСТОРИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена роль методов формирования дидактической культуры будущих учителей истории, основные направления деятельности учителя, социальные отношения, его основные задачи.

Ключевые слова: методическая культура, информационная культура, учитель, информационные системы, урок, метод, будущее.

INTRODUCTION

Effectiveness of the educational process is one of the reforms implemented in the modern education system. Also, arousing interest in education is one of the urgent issues of today. The source of interest in the continuing education system is the content of the educational material. The content of the educational material should be bright, rich in news, descriptive, and create a feeling of wonder, moral and spiritual state, and the importance of the seminar should be shown. For this purpose, interesting examples, facts, video and individual tools, newspapers, radio messages are selected that can arouse students' interest. Interest in education can be realized through educational games. The following requirements are imposed on them:

1. *Compatibility with the curriculum.*
2. *Pursuit of certain educational goals.*
3. *Compliance with certain consistency.*
4. *Taking into account individual characteristics of students.*
5. *Simple and clear setting of game rules.*
6. *Active participation of every student.*

A teacher responsible for himself must clearly understand that his professional training, the right to be a teacher, and the proper fulfillment of his professional pedagogical duty require him to take on a number of obligations. he should objectively assess his opportunities for teaching activity, study and analyze his strengths, clearly imagine which qualities are professionally important in the process of professional training and which should be formed independently, in the process of real professional pedagogical activity.

Secondly, the future history teacher must master intellectual activity (thinking, memory, perception, expression of attention), behavior and communication culture, including pedagogical skills.

Thirdly, the mandatory condition and basis of the successful activity of the teacher is his understanding of the student as an equivalent person with the same self-esteem as his "I", knowing the forms of behavior and communication. Students, the learner, their values, behaviors and evaluations must be understood and accepted by the teacher whether they are appropriate or not.

Fourthly, the teacher is not only an organizer, but also inspires the cooperation of participants in educational activities, works as a partner in activities to achieve the general, in a certain sense, goals of education, upbringing and development.

Self-education is the basis for the teacher's growth as a specialist. The teacher, according to A. Disterweg, "has only worked on education and training on his own so far without actually being able to teach and teach". It is not enough to say that if he does not study, does not study, does not follow the achievements of science in his field and does not put them into practice, he is left behind, pulled back, and has difficulty in solving problems.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The desire and experience of self-improvement is a necessary condition for self-education, which includes conscious work to develop professionally significant qualities of one's personality in three directions:

- adaptation of individual characteristics to the requirements of pedagogical activity;
- continuous improvement of professional qualifications;
- c) continuous development of socio-ethical and other characteristics of a person.

In order to correctly set self-education goals, you need to know your strengths and weaknesses.

Means and methods of self-influence:

Didactic abilities are manifested in the following: a) explanatory ability, that is, the ability to see and hear students with their own eyes, to be able to make incomprehensible terms understandable, simple and universal; b) academic abilities, in other words, knowledge of the subject, field of science, erudition, broad outlook are considered as the result of self-work; c) speech skills, the ability to express one's thoughts and feelings clearly and clearly in the form of speech, to conduct speech in combination with non-verbal means of communication, that is, mimicry and pantomime. From this, knowing the subject, believing in the words he is telling, avoiding complex phraseological expressions, explaining the used terms and concepts, speed and pitch of speech.

Organizational and communicative skills are characterized by the following qualities:

organizational skills, in which it is necessary to define 2 directions of activity - first, to organize a team of learners, and second, to properly organize one's work, plan and self-control, study taking into account that the process is limited in terms of time, maximum effort is required from the teacher to convey knowledge;

communicative abilities - to establish a correct interaction with a group of learners, an individual, taking into account their individual and age characteristics; it should be known from the middle of two boundaries - cold alienation and family relations;

pedagogical observation or, as A.S. Makarenko said, "The ability to read by looking at the surface", that is, the ability to enter the inner world of the learner, intelligence, understanding of the student's personality and understanding of his temporary mental states. Of course, these are influenced by external factors, student behavior and pedagogical experience;

pedagogical tactics - that is, the ability to find appropriate measures to influence students, taking into account their individual and other characteristics, based on a concrete situation, without affecting the personality of a person;

suggestive ability - the ability to have an emotional-volitional influence on students, to make demands and fulfill them, without any pressure and coercion, at the same time gentleness and unwillingness;

pedagogical imagination, the ability to foresee the consequences of one's actions, the educational design of the personality of learners, the ability to foresee the development of one or another quality of the learner;

distribution of attention, distribution of one's attention between several objects and activities, i.e. presentation of material, monitoring the development of thoughts, answering questions in time, controlling the behavior of a group of learners.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Pedagogical technology determines the system of professionally important skills of pedagogues. It offers ways to understand the technological nature of pedagogical activity in order to influence the learner.

Each pedagogue organizes the impact on the learner according to many parameters. Emotional - mental state, the general level of age-related and cultural development, the formation of relationships, spiritual and intellectual development, etc. In the end, the personality of the student is formed in every primary imagination on the basis of the external manifestation. It determines the character of the pedagogical effect in many ways.

From the point of view of pedagogical technology, scientists have defined the general rules for the application of the method of pedagogical influence with the principle requirements of pedagogy:

The harmony of demand and respect for students.

Preparation of any pedagogical effect.

Bringing this effect to the end.

Ability to feel responsibility for the result of education.

Taking out each of these regulations, it is worth noting that all of them are directed to the development of students' cognitive activity and interest in the subject and result.

It should not be forgotten that the success of education largely depends on the pedagogue, his high professional skills, and his personal characteristics.

DISCUSSION

Didactic foundations of the educational process. The educational process consists of the activities of the pedagogue and students, and certain educational tasks are solved, that is, knowledge, skills and abilities are acquired, and the personality of the student is formed. The educational process consists of the following elements:

1. Determination of educational goals.

2. Educational content that ensures the implementation of educational goals is presented in programs and textbooks.

3. Educational principles, methods and tools.

4. Forms of education.

5. Determination of educational results and determination of the next direction.

Hence, the pedagogue, when planning the educational process, prepares for each subject taking into account the above elements. The educational process is interconnected, forms a complex system.

The following four elements must be included in the educational content:

1. Knowledge of the world, objective being.
2. Skills and competencies based on knowledge.
3. Criteria for creative activity.
4. The embodiment of universal, spiritual values.

Each of these elements performs specific tasks in the maturation of the individual. According to I.Ya.Lerner, M.N.Skatkin's theory, this direction can be widely interpreted. Through knowledge, skills and abilities are formed, as a result of solving various problems, creative activity is formed, and a certain system of relationships arises in a person with respect to other people, being, Nature, oneself, emotions awaken.

The educational process is characterized by general laws, and the identification of these laws helps to develop ways of conscious and effective management of education. Didactic principles are a theoretical basis for understanding the educational process. On the basis of didactic principles, it is possible to develop clear, scientifically verified instructions about the organization of teaching.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that the role of methodology in the formation of the didactic culture of future history teachers is considered one of the important issues in the educational system, therefore, education through the formation of the didactic culture of future history teachers through methodical processes shows that many successes can be achieved in the system.

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